

APPENDIX

Comparison of ParlaSent to dictionary and GPT-based approaches

Data

To validate the ParlaSent model and compare it with older as well as newer approaches, we use two external evaluation datasets not used for training or evaluation of the ParlaSent model. First dataset was released as a part of replication data for Proksch et. al. (2019) and consists of annotated speeches presented during the annual State of the European Union debate in 2010. We namely focus on three files: `1_coding_a_2010.tab`, `1_coding_b_2010.tab`, and `1_coding_c_2010.tab`. These three files contain English text segments with average length of about 500 characters and 578 human annotations on a 5-step Likert scale. The second validation dataset comes from Rauh’s replication repository (2018) and contains texts sampled from the plenary sessions of the German Bundestag. The dataset (`DE_bundestag`) consists of two CSV files with a common index. One file contains, among other attributes, lower-cased single-sentence text, the ‘Net Tone’ defined by Young and Soroka (2012), and what we will refer to as the ‘dictionary score’. The other file includes human annotations from three annotators and the final ‘vote,’ which can be mapped onto a 5-step Likert scale. This dataset contains 1,500 instances. Since the instances consist of single sentences only, the average character length is shorter than its English counterpart, at 140 characters.

Dictionary approach

ParlaSent XLM-R model performance was compared with two very different approaches. On one hand, we used the tried-and-true dictionary-based approach, using the English Lexicoder Sentiment Dictionary (Young and Soroka 2012) on our English validation dataset. From the obtained counts of positive and negative terms we calculated Young and Soroka (2012) ‘Net Tone’ dictionary scores. In the case of the German validation dataset, we omit this step entirely, because the dataset provides the

positive and negative terms counts and dictionary scores already, thus providing a benchmark/sanity check for our implementation on the English validation dataset.

GPT-based approach

The instruction-tuned generative pre-trained transformer models (GPTs), initially developed for text generation, have recently demonstrated promising performance also on various other natural language processing tasks, such as stance detection (Zhang et al. 2024), implicit hate speech categorization (Huang, Kwak, and An 2023), news topic classification (Kuzman and Ljubešić 2024), automatic genre identification (Kuzman, Mozetič, and Ljubešić 2023), causal commonsense reasoning (Ljubešić et al. 2024), and machine translation (Hendy et al. 2023). To evaluate the competitiveness of the ParlaSent model relative to GPT models, we conducted an additional assessment of the performance of the GPT-4o model by the OpenAI (OpenAI 2024) on the German (Rauh 2018) and English test datasets (Proksch et al. 2019).

In these experiments, we use the GPT-4o model, namely the version `gpt-4o-2024-08-06`, via the OpenAI API. The model is used in a zero-shot prompting scenario, which means that it is not provided with examples of the training data, but only with a description of the task and the labels. As with the experiments with the ParlaSent model, the task is formulated as a regression problem. The GPT model is required to evaluate the sentiment of the provided texts with a continuous value from 0 to 6, where a value of 0 corresponds to an extremely negative sentiment, while a value of 6 indicates an extremely positive sentiment. The prompt that is provided to the model along with the texts includes a description of the task and the labels, as shown in Figure A1.

Figure A1: The prompt that is provided to the GPT-4o model, comprising the description of the task and the sentiment labels.

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    ### Task
    Your task is to analyze the sentiment in the provided parliamentary text, meaning that you need to recognize whether the speaker's sentiment towards the topic is negative, neutral, positive or somewhere in between. You will be provided with an excerpt from a parliamentary speech in {lang} language, delimited by single quotation marks. You should provide the information on the sentiment as a continuous value between 0 and 6 where 0 is extremely negative and 6 is extremely positive. Always provide a label, even if you are not sure.

    ### Output format
    Return a valid JSON dictionary with the following key: 'sentiment' and a value should be a float between 0 and 6 according to this label description:

    - "negative - text that is entirely or predominantly negative": 0 <= label < 1
    - "mixed sentiment but overall negative - text that conveys an ambiguous sentiment or a mixture of sentiments, but leans more towards the negative sentiment in a positive-negative classification": 1 <= label < 2 ,
    - "neutral with negative tendency - text that only contains non-sentiment-related statements, but still leans more towards the negative sentiment in a positive-negative classification": 2 <= label < 3 ,
    - "neutral with positive tendency - text that only contains non-sentiment-related statements, but still leans more towards the positive sentiment in a positive-negative classification": 3 <= label < 4,
    - "mixed sentiment but overall positive - text that conveys an ambiguous sentiment or a mixture of sentiments, but leans more towards the positive sentiment in a positive-negative classification": 4 <= label < 5,
    - "positive - text that is entirely or predominantly positive": 5 <= label < 6

    Text: '{text}'

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Results

The scale of the scores obtained in this way varies greatly, human annotations use a 5-step Likert scale, ParlaSent model and the GPT-4o model output real numbers between 0 and 6, and dictionary scores range between -1 and 1, inclusively. To compare performances on these different scales, we use the Spearman rank-order correlation coefficient, which is close to 1 for samples with strong ordinal correlation, 0 in cases where no ordinal correlation exists, and close to -1 for samples with strong negative ordinal correlation. Table A1 summarizes the performance across all three tested strategies.

Table A1: Comparison of performance

	Dictionary score	ParlaSent model	GPT-4o
English test dataset	0.409	0.800	0.837
German test dataset	0.408	0.772	0.777

Note: Comparison of performance of the dictionary score approach, the ParlaSent model and the GPT-4o model on English and German test datasets in terms of Spearman's correlation between the predicted values and human annotations. All Spearman correlation coefficients are significant on $p < 0.001$.

Comparison of different approaches shows that manual annotations correlate positively with dictionary scores as expected, but both the ParlaSent model and GPT-4o outperform them drastically on both datasets. The GPT-4o model performs similarly as the ParlaSent model on the German test dataset, and slightly outperforms the ParlaSent model on the English dataset with a four point higher Spearman correlation coefficient. While the GPT model provides a slight improvement in performance, its use comes with higher computational costs. Furthermore, using the GPT model via the API leads to considerably slower inference times compared to running the ParlaSent model locally. Specifically, generating labels for 1,500 German test instances took nearly 30 minutes, while inference with the ParlaSent model completed after 15 seconds. This slow inference makes the GPT model impractical for large-scale sentiment annotation tasks, such as the automatic labeling of millions of texts – an approach successfully implemented with the ParlaSent model on the ParlaMint corpora.

We finally plot a pairwise comparison of the results between the gold annotations and all three approaches for English in Figure A2 and German in Figure A3. The scatter-plot comparisons between model outputs and the gold labels follow the previously reported Spearman correlation coefficients, but also note the fact that GPT-4o is not using very much the opportunity to return real values anywhere between 0 and 6, but rather sticks to 10 different values. These figures also show a difference in the distribution of the three implied categories (positive, neutral, negative) in the outputs of the three models. There is a visible trend of the dictionary approach to the “neutral” output due to the limited coverage of the lexicons, and the approach defaulting to a “neutral” prediction if no trend through the lexicon is identified. ParlaSent is obviously biased primarily towards negative, but also towards positive sentiment when compared to the gold labels. GPT-4o is slightly less biased towards the neutral sentiment in comparison to the gold labels. These insights show what is inherent to each model - dictionaries lack coverage, ParlaSent was developed with negativity in political communication in mind, while GPT-4o, a generic tool, is less critical than annotators in the English and German data annotation tasks. We do not consider the biases of ParlaSent and GPT-4o to be an

issue, but rather their feature that has to be taken into consideration when using each method. Important is that we have shown that the order of instances is of similar quality both in the output of ParlaSent and GPT-4o, while the output of the dictionary approach simply lags behind due to the lack of lexicon coverage, but also insensibility to words in context.

Figure A2: Comparison of gold (i.e. human annotated) labels, dictionary scores, ParlaSent and GPT-4o annotations on the English validation dataset.

Figure A3: Comparison of gold (i.e. human annotated) labels, dictionary scores, ParlaSent and GPT-4o annotations on the German validation dataset.

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